

Review

A Comprehensive Look at Low Back Pain: A Dual Perspective from Western and Traditional Chinese Medicine (Part 1).

Ermelinda Leitão^{1*}, Ana Carina Neves¹, Andreia Santos³, Alexandra Monteiro¹, and Inês Reis Sousa¹.

¹ Independent researcher;

² Quarteira Medical Centre/Centro Médico de Quarteira, Loulé, Faro, Portugal;

³ Estarreja Medical Centre/Centro Médico de Estarreja, Aveiro, Portugal.

* Correspondence: ermelinda.r.santos@gmail.com

Abstract

Low back pain is a prevalent health issue affecting a significant portion of the global population, with a lifetime incidence of 60–70% in industrialised countries. It is the leading cause of years lived with disability worldwide, placing a considerable burden on individuals, families, and society due to its impact on quality of life, work productivity, and healthcare costs.

Western medicine classifies low back pain based on its duration (acute or chronic) and origin (specific or non-specific).

Acute low back pain is typically short-term and caused by sudden injuries, while chronic low back pain persists for over three months and can involve biological, psychological, and social factors.

Specific low back pain has a clear, identifiable cause, such as a herniated disc, spinal stenosis, or arthritis. On the other hand, non-specific low back pain, which accounts for about 90% of cases, lacks a clear structural cause and is often linked to muscle tension or poor posture. Diagnosis in Western medicine involves a physical exam and may include imaging techniques like X-rays, MRI, or CT scans to identify underlying issues. Treatment is primarily conservative, including rest, heat/cold application, medication, and physiotherapy, with surgery reserved for severe, persistent cases.

In contrast, Traditional Chinese Medicine views low back pain as a symptom of an imbalance in the flow of *Qi* (vital energy) and *Xue* (blood). The lumbar region is associated with the Kidneys, considered the "root of life". Traditional Chinese Medicine categorises the causes of low back pain into three main patterns: Kidney deficiency (often linked to chronic, age-related pain), external pathogenic factors such as cold, humidity, or wind, and stagnation of *Qi* and/or *Xue*. The goal of Traditional Chinese Medicine treatment is to restore the balance of *Qi* and *Xue*, strengthen the Kidneys, and expel external factors.

This document provides an overview of low back pain from both Western and Traditional Chinese Medicine perspectives, setting the stage for a subsequent exploratory review of Traditional Chinese Medicine techniques for managing this condition.

Keywords: Low Back Pain; Western Medicine; Traditional Chinese Medicine.

Citation: Leitão E., Neves A.C., Monteiro C., Silva H., Santos A., Monteiro A., Sousa I.R. A Comprehensive Look at Low Back Pain: A Dual Perspective from Western and Traditional Chinese Medicine (Part 1). *Journal of Complementary Therapies in Health*. 2025;3(3) 10.5281/zenodo.17112549

Academic Editor: Jorge Rodrigues

Received: 23 June 2025

Reviewed: 12 July 2025

Revised: 12 August 2025

Accepted: 13 August 2025

Published: 15 August 2025

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1. Background

Low back pain, also known as lumbar pain, is the pain that affects the lower region of the spine, from the base of the ribs to the area above the buttocks. It is not a disease, but rather a symptom that can be associated with various conditions. It is an extremely common health problem that affects a large part of the world's population at some point in their lives ^{1,2}.

In fact, the incidence and prevalence of low back pain make it one of the most significant health problems globally. The World Health Organization (WHO) and other epidemiological studies indicate that pain in the lumbar region affects approximately 60-70% of the population in industrialised countries at some point in their lives, and that at any time, between 12% and 33% of the population suffers from low back pain³⁻⁵. This condition is the leading cause of years lived with disability worldwide^{6,7}.

Low back pain imposes an enormous burden, not only on individuals, but on their families and on society in general. For the individual and family, chronic pain can have a devastating impact on quality of life. People with severe low back pain may have difficulty performing basic daily tasks, such as getting dressed, walking, or sleeping⁸⁻¹⁰. Physical restrictions affect participation in social and leisure activities, leading to social isolation¹¹⁻¹³. In addition, persistent pain is often associated with anxiety, depression, and a decline in mental health^{14,15}. For families, the burden is emotional and, often, financial, with increased medical expenses and the need to provide care¹⁶⁻¹⁸. For society and the economy, low back pain is one of the main reasons for loss of work productivity and absenteeism, and indirect costs, such as lost wages and decreased productivity, often exceed direct healthcare costs¹⁹⁻²². The management of low back pain, including medical consultations, physiotherapy, medication, and, in rare cases, surgery, requires huge resources from public and private health systems^{22,23}.

1.1. Anatomy and Structures of the Lumbar Spine

The spinal column (Figure 1), especially the lumbar portion (Figure 1), is a complex anatomical structure, crucial for supporting body weight and for movement. It is in its complex composition that the origins of a large part of low back pain are found²⁴⁻²⁶.

Figure 1. Spinal Column (left) and respective lumbar vertebrae (right) viewed laterally²⁷.

The base of this structure is formed by vertebrae L1 to L5, the five lowest vertebrae of the spine ²⁷. These (Figure 2) are robust and larger than their counterparts in the thoracic (Figure 3) and cervical (Figure 4) sections, and are designed to support most of the body's weight ²⁶. Their shape and alignment, with the natural curvature of the spine, are fundamental for an upright posture and for the proper distribution of loads ^{25,28}.

Figure 2. Lumbar vertebrae viewed from above ²⁷.

Figure 3. Thoracic vertebrae viewed from above ²⁷.

Figure 4. Cervical (2nd) vertebrae viewed from above ²⁷.

Between each lumbar vertebra, there are intervertebral discs. Acting as natural shock absorbers, they are fibrocartilaginous structures that absorb the impact of daily movements, such as walking, jumping, or lifting weights^{29,30}. Their gel-like composition gives them flexibility and the ability to protect the vertebrae from damage^{29,30}.

In addition, the stability and mobility of the spine are guaranteed by a complex system of muscles, ligaments, and tendons. The spinal erector muscles (Figure 5) and abdominal muscles (Figure 5) are crucial examples for trunk stability and posture maintenance^{31,32}. When these muscles are weak, tense, or imbalanced, the lumbar spine becomes more vulnerable to injuries^{33,34}.

Figure 5. Erector Spinae muscles (left) and abdominal wall (right)²⁷.

Finally, the lumbar region is the point of origin of vital nerves that extend to the rest of the body^{35,36}. The most notable is the sciatic nerve (Figure 6), the largest nerve in the human body, which originates in the lower spine and descends into the legs^{27,37}. When

surrounding structures, such as a herniated disc, compress this nerve, the pain can radiate down the leg³⁸.

Figure 6. Sciatic nerve (ischiadic/*ischiadicus*)²⁷.

1.2. Types of Low Back Pain

Low back pain does not manifest uniformly, and its classification helps determine the most appropriate therapeutic approach^{39,40}. Western medicine categorises low back pain based on its duration and its origin.

Regarding duration, it can be acute or chronic.

Acute low back pain is characterised by short-term pain that usually resolves in a few weeks, up to a maximum of six weeks. It is normally the result of a sudden injury, such as

lifting a weight incorrectly, a sudden movement, or trauma. The pain can be intense, but it tends to decrease with rest and simple care ^{41,42}.

On the other hand, chronic low back pain refers to pain that persists for a long period, longer than three months. Chronic low back pain is not just the continuation of acute pain; it often involves biological, psychological, and social factors that can hinder recovery ^{43,44}.

With regard to its cause, it can be specific or non-specific low back pain.

Specific low back pain occurs when the pain has a clear and identifiable origin ⁴⁵. Examples include a herniated disc, where the intervertebral disc puts pressure on a nerve ⁴⁶; spinal stenosis, a narrowing of the spinal canal that compresses the spinal cord and nerves ⁴⁷; or conditions such as arthritis ⁴⁸, fractures, or tumours, although the latter are very rare ^{49,50}.

In opposition, nonspecific low back pain is the most common form of low back pain, representing around 90% of cases ³. In this case, the exact cause of the pain cannot be identified through imaging exams, such as magnetic resonance imaging or X-rays. The pain is believed to be related to muscle tension, excessive exertion, or poor posture, without significant structural damage ^{3,51}.

1.3. Common Causes for Low Back Pain

Low back pain can have various causes, but most cases are associated with mechanical or structural problems in the spinal column and surrounding tissues ^{52,53}. As superficially mentioned earlier, there are several possible mechanical causes.

Muscle tension and ligament injury are the most frequent causes of acute low back pain. It occurs when there is excessive strain on the muscles or ligaments in the lumbar region, often due to a sudden movement, incorrect weight lifting, prolonged poor posture, or lack of warming up before exercise ⁵⁴⁻⁵⁶. The tension causes inflammation and pain, but tends to improve with rest and physiotherapy ^{55,57}.

A herniated disc occurs when the nucleus projects out through a fissure in the ring. This protrusion can compress the spinal nerves that pass nearby, causing an acute pain that can radiate to the leg ^{30,58}.

Moreover, the spinal canal is the space that houses the spinal cord and nerves ^{1,59}. Spinal stenosis is the abnormal narrowing of the spinal canal. This narrowing can be congenital or, more often, the result of degenerative changes associated with ageing, such as the growth of bone spurs ^{47,60}. Nerve compression can cause pain, numbness, and weakness in the legs, especially when walking ⁶¹.

Finally, arthritis can also arise as a cause of low back pain. Osteoarthritis is the most common form of arthritis that affects the spine. The degeneration of cartilage in the facet joints of the vertebrae can lead to inflammation and pain ^{62,63}.

However, although most low back pain is of mechanical origin, in rarer cases, the pain can be a symptom of a more serious underlying medical condition. Examples include osteoporosis, which weakens the bones and can lead to compression fractures in the vertebrae ^{64,65}; spinal tumours ⁶⁶ or infections in the spine ^{67,68}. As expected, these cases require an urgent medical evaluation.

1.4. Diagnosis and Conventional Treatment

The diagnosis and treatment of low back pain in Western medicine follow a progressive approach, focusing first on ruling out serious conditions and then on managing the symptoms ^{69,70}. The diagnostic process begins with a detailed physical exam, where the doctor evaluates posture, range of motion of the spine, and reflexes. This exam allows them to identify the location and intensity of the pain, as well as to detect signs of nerve compression or muscle weakness ^{71,72}.

In cases of persistent pain, pain that radiates to the legs, or suspicion of a more serious underlying cause, the doctor may request imaging exams ^{73,74}. These can be: (1) X-ray to identify bone problems, such as fractures, tumors, or spinal misalignment ⁷⁵⁻⁷⁸; (2) magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), which is considered the gold standard for evaluating soft

tissues, such as discs and nerves, is essential for diagnosing herniated discs or spinal stenosis ^{79,80}; and (3), computed tomography (CT) scan offers a more detailed view of the bone structures ^{81,82}.

With regard to the treatment of low back pain, this is, in most cases, conservative ⁸³. Options include:

- Rest and activity moderation: Initial rest can be beneficial, but prolonged inactivity is not recommended. It is crucial to stay active within the limits of the pain ^{84,85}.
- Application of Heat/Cold: Applying ice can reduce inflammation in the initial phase of acute pain, while heat can relax muscles and relieve tension ⁸⁶. However, this approach is controversial ⁸⁷.
- Medications: Analgesics (such as paracetamol) and non-steroidal anti-inflammatories are often prescribed for the relief of pain and inflammation ^{88,89}. However, the guidelines from the World Health Organization ⁸³ suggest a cautious approach. The use of non-steroidal anti-inflammatories is recommended with a moderate degree of certainty, but their use must be limited and considered. In contrast, the guidelines from the World Health Organization ⁸³ advise against the use of paracetamol (acetaminophen) and opioids as a first-line treatment for chronic low back pain, due to their low effectiveness or potential for serious side effects and addiction.
- Physiotherapy: Physiotherapy is a vital component of treatment. Exercises to strengthen core muscles, stretches, and manipulations help improve posture, increase flexibility, and prevent the recurrence of pain ^{90,91}.

In cases of persistent pain that does not respond to conservative treatments, more invasive interventions may be considered. Corticosteroid injections directly into the painful area can provide temporary relief by reducing inflammation around the nerve roots ^{92,93}.

Surgery is always a last resort, reserved for a small number of patients with severe and persistent low back pain, usually when there is a clear and identifiable structural cause that does not improve with other approaches, such as a herniated disc that compresses a nerve ^{94,95}.

2. Traditional Chinese Medicine and Low Back Pain

In Traditional Chinese Medicine, low back pain is not seen as an isolated problem of bones or muscles, but rather as a symptom of an imbalance in the circulation of *Qi* (vital energy) and *Xue* (blood) in the body ⁹⁶. Traditional Chinese Medicine associates the lumbar region with the Kidneys, which are considered the "root of life" and the source of our essence ⁹⁶. Pain is a sign that the flow of *Qi* in the meridians that cross the lumbar area is blocked or deficient.

In Traditional Chinese Medicine, the causes of low back pain are commonly classified into three main categories:

- Kidney Deficiency: This is the most natural cause, especially in chronic and age-related low back pain. Kidney *Qi* deficiency can result from ageing, overwork, or pregnancy and has characteristics such as dull and recurrent vague pain ⁹⁶⁻⁹⁸.
- According to Birch *et al.* ⁹⁹, Kidney deficiency can also be *Yin* or *Yang*, with their corresponding signs (cold, weakness/heat due to deficiency).
- Attack of External Pathogenic Factors: Prolonged exposure to environmental factors, such as Cold, Humidity, or Wind, can invade the meridians and cause blockages. According to Xiong *et al.* ⁹⁷, Cold and Humidity are among the most relevant factors associated with chronic low back pain. Birch *et al.* ⁹⁹ add Wind to this list.
- Stagnation of *Qi* and/or *Xue* ⁹⁷⁻⁹⁹: According to Xiong *et al.* ⁹⁷, this factor includes signs such as piercing pain, limited activity due to a local feeling of heaviness, stiffness in the lower back and flanks with limited flexion, and a purplish tongue.

However, Xiong *et al.*⁹⁷ also refer to a fourth factor, rarely mentioned in the literature. This is a Heat pattern in which the diagnostic characteristics focus on the presence of a purple tongue, a yellow coating on the tongue, and burning pain⁹⁷. This pattern is also mentioned by Birch *et al.*⁹⁹. This pattern appears associated with an acute condition; however, as the analyses of Xiong *et al.*⁹⁷ and Birch *et al.*⁹⁹ focused on patients with chronic low back pain, it is inferred that this is a factor attributed to an acute phase of chronic low back pain.

Figure 7 provides an overall overview according to the theory provided by the authors.

Figure 7. Main Traditional Chinese Medicine theories explaining back pain.

Based on the information above, it is expected that the treatment of low back pain in Traditional Chinese Medicine aims to restore the flow of *Qi* and *Xue*, strengthen the Kidney, and expel external pathogenic factors.

Within this framework, Part II of this research will explore the evidence on Traditional Chinese Medicine for low back pain. The second part will be an exploratory review that will focus on the analysis of current evidence on the diverse traditional Chinese medicine techniques for the management of low back pain, built on the foundation of this contextual first part research.

Building upon the foundational understanding of low back pain from a Western medical perspective, Part II of this study will delve into the evidence for Traditional Chinese Medicine therapies. The second part will provide an exploratory review, analysing current high-level evidence on the diverse techniques used in Traditional Chinese Medicine for managing low back pain. By establishing this contextual framework, this research

aims to provide a comprehensive look at how these ancient practices can serve as a valuable complement to modern conventional treatments.

Credit author statement: Conceptualization, E.L.; Methodology, E.L.; Validation, E.L.; Formal analysis, E.L., A.C.N., C.M., H.S., A.S., A.M., and I.R.S.; Investigation, E.L., A.C.N., C.M., H.S., A.S., A.M., and I.R.S.; Resources, E.L.; Writing - Original Draft, E.L.; Writing - Review & Editing, E.L., A.C.N., C.M., H.S., A.S., A.M., and I.R.S.; Visualization, E.L.; Project administration, E.L., A.C.N., C.M., H.S., A.S., A.M., and I.R.S. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research did not receive any specific grant from funding agencies in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors.

Conflict of Interest: The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: The original contributions presented in this study are included in the article. Further inquiries can be directed to the corresponding author.

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